

**POLICY DEVELOPMENT FOR INCLUSIVE
TERTIARY EDUCATION in UGANDA -
*MANDELA WASHINGTON FELLOWSHIP
EXCHANGE PROGRAM***

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Abstract

Background

Uganda has embraced inclusive education and evidently committed itself to bringing about disability inclusion at every level of education. Both legal and non-legal frameworks have been adopted and arguably are in line with the intent of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) on education. The CRPD, in Article 24, requires states to attain a right to education for persons with disabilities without discrimination and on the basis of equal opportunities at all levels of education.

Uganda has committed itself to uphold the UN Human Rights norms by ratifying various UN human rights treaties,¹ including the recently adopted CRPD. The current constitution of Uganda reflects a similar commitment. Chapter four of the constitution guarantees protection and enjoyment of fundamental rights and freedoms to every citizen. Article 21 of the constitution, generally reaffirms the principle of chapter four that the enshrined fundamental rights and freedoms of the individuals in the constitution are inherent and not granted by the State; and that, these rights and freedoms shall be respected, upheld and promoted by all organs and agencies of government and by all persons.

Objectives

Despite Uganda's robust disability legal and policy framework on education, there is evidence of exclusion and discrimination of students with disabilities in the higher education institutions. The main objective of this article is to explore the status of disability inclusion in higher education and strategies for its realization, using evidence from Emong's study, workshop proceedings where the authors facilitated

¹ According to the UN Treaty Body Data Base, as at November 2010, out of the 9 UN human rights treaties, Uganda has either accessed or ratified 8 and signed one. However, has not taken action on three UN human rights optional protocols, namely, Second Optional to the International Covenant on the Civil and Political Rights (CCPR- OP 2- DP) Optional Protocol to the International Covenant on the Economic, Social and Cultural Right (ICESCR-OP) and the Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Elimination of forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW- OP).

and additional individual interviews with four students with disabilities by the authors.

Results

The results show that there are discrimination and exclusion tendencies in matters related to admissions, access to lectures, assessment and examinations, access to library services, halls of residence and other disability support services.

Conclusion

The article recommends that institutional policies and guidelines on support services for students with disabilities and special needs in higher education be developed, data on students with disabilities collected to help planning, collaboration between Disabled People's Organisations (DPO's) strengthened to ensure disability inclusion and the establishment of disability support centers.

THE RIGHT OF PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES IN UGANDA: THE LEGAL AND POLICY FRAMEWORK

Introduction

Uganda has embraced inclusive education and evidently committed itself to bringing about disability inclusion at every level of education. The commitment is demonstrated by the legal and non-legal frameworks on education and the establishment of educational infrastructure aimed at mainstreaming disability. The infrastructures include a department of special needs education at the Ministry of Education, Science, Technology and Sports, a special needs education section at the Uganda National Examinations Board, a department at the National Curriculum Development Centre, a section at the Education Standards Agency, representation of persons with disabilities at the National Council for Higher Education Board, Public Universities Councils and training of teachers for special needs education². The bulk of these infrastructures are visible in promoting inclusive education at primary and secondary levels of education.

There is however, *affirmative action* on admission of students with disabilities and other marginalized groups to public universities. Although this affirmative action is

² <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5433449/#abstract1>

seen to be widening opportunities for students with disabilities to higher education, the law providing for it appears not to compel private universities³ to comply.

The right to education for students with disabilities in Uganda is still suffering from discrimination. Disability rights are often honoured in the breach, which leads to failure to achieve equal opportunities particularly in higher education.

International law is emphatic that the right of education in general, and for LWDs in particular, must be guaranteed at all times. Beginning with the *1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)*⁴, subsequent treaties secure every person's right to education, including the *1976 International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights*⁵ (*ICCPR*), *International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights*⁶ (*ICESCR*), *Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women*⁷ (*CEDAW*) and *African (Banjul) Charter on Human and People's Rights (Banjul Charter)*⁸. In the context of LWDs, *the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD)* contains a comprehensive protection framework⁹. In addition to this international framework, several countries have passed domestic legislation¹⁰.

Whilst Uganda is in the international limelight for its disability inclusion with regards to political participation of its disabled people and having a strong, articulate and representative disability movement,¹¹ Its literature on disability inclusion in higher education is rare. Further, while comprehensive reviews of Uganda higher

³ See the wording of section 28 of the Universities and other Tertiary Institutions Act 2001 (as amended).

⁴ Universal Declaration of Human Rights, G.A. Res. 217 (III) A, art. 26 (Dec. 10, 1948) [hereinafter UDHR].

⁵ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, art. 7, Dec. 16, 1966, 999 U.N.T.S. 171 (1967) [hereinafter ICCPR].

⁶ International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, art. 13, Dec. 16, 1966, 993 U.N.T.S. 3 (1967) [hereinafter ICESCR].

⁷ Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, art. 5, Dec. 18, 1979, 1249 U.N.T.S. 13 (1980).

⁸ African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, art. 17(1), June 27, 1981, 1520 U.N.T.S. 217 (1982) [hereinafter African Charter].

⁹ Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, Dec. 13, 2006, 2515 U.N.T.S. 3 (2008) [hereinafter CRPD].

¹⁰ See, e.g., Persons with Disabilities Act, 2010 (No. 10) (Tanz.); Public Health and Disability Act, 2000 (N.Z.); Discrimination Against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2018 (Nigeria).

¹¹ AK Dube, 'Participation of Disabled People in the PRSP/PEAP in Uganda' in B Albert (ed), *In or out of Mainstream? Lessons from Research on Disability and Development Cooperation* (Leeds Disability Press, Leeds 2006) 134.

education have been undertaken by funding bodies¹² and the National Council for Higher Education (NCHE)¹³ disabled students are still invisible in these reports. Again, while national reviews on disability have been undertaken by the national disability organizations and by international development partners,¹⁴ These reports contain scant information on how institutions of higher education are including the disabled people. This study aims to contribute to this literature by filling these gaps.

Collectively, this corpus of law requires education providers to respect and promote the right of access to university education by all persons, including LWDs. Yet, access to an academic institution by itself is insufficient. In order to achieve the underlying legal obligation, all learners must be able to access the entire physical environment. Institutions must therefore provide all necessary tools, to ensure that LWDs, like other learners, may continue with their education journey uninterrupted. This obligation calls on universities to remove all barriers of access to education¹⁵. The drafters of the CRPD were concerned that, despite various institutions and undertakings, LWDs continued to face barriers in their participation as equal members of society. Consequently, the Preamble to the treaty recognized the importance of accessibility to educational facilities as well as other types of facilities¹⁶.

Universities have a legal obligation to remove all physical barriers and obstacles preventing the full integration and participation of LWDs. This article focuses on the right to education for LWDs. It also considers measures that could be taken to ensure this right is implemented. Using Uganda as a case study, this article reviews the situation in select universities throughout the country.

Uganda's legal framework is consistent with its international counterpart. The rights and obligations contained domestically are reinforced at the international level. As

¹² See X Liang, 'Uganda Tertiary Education Sector' (Human Development Sector, African Region, World Bank 2004).
http://siteresources.worldbank.org/AFRICAEXT/Resources/no_50.pdf accessed on 23rd September 2010.

¹³ See National Council for Higher Education, 'State of Higher Education and Training in Uganda 2006: A report on Higher Education Delivery and Institutions' and 'State of Higher Education and Training in Uganda 2005: A report on Higher Education Delivery and Institutions' <http://www.unche.or.ug/brief.php?id=26>

¹⁴ R Lang and A Murangira, 'Disability Scoping Study' (DFID Commissioned Study Report 2009).

¹⁵ See UNESCO, Guidelines for Inclusion; Ensuring Access to Education for All (2005), <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000140224> (May 24, 2020); Paul M. Gichana, Challenges Facing the Implementation of Inclusive Education Programme in Public Primary Schools in Mombasa District of Kenya 15-25 (2009) (M.A. thesis, University of Nairobi) (on file with author).

¹⁶ CRPD, *supra* note 12, pmb. v.

with the situation in Kenya, international legal provisions reiterate the fundamental right to education as well as the norms of non-discrimination and dignity for all learners. *Article 24(1) of the CRPD* requires universities to ensure LWDs enjoy the right to education at all times¹⁷. These institutions are also prohibited from discriminating against these learners¹⁸. This treaty requires them to guarantee to LWDs all the rights that are due to them. These provisions are designed to create a level playing ground for all learners.

To this end, *Articles 5 and 24(2)(c) of the CRPD require universities to take “reasonable accommodation” steps, as a way towards realizing the rights to inclusion, non-discrimination, and equality for LWDs*¹⁹. These principles are fundamental to the enjoyment of the right to education. What do the terms “discrimination” and “discrimination against LWDs” mean? It is important for us to understand the meanings of these terms. Otherwise how can one establish the extent to which an academic institution is complying with the obligations due to LWDs? The prohibition against discrimination is well-known. At the international level Article 2 of the *UDHR declares that “[e]veryone is entitled to all the rights set forth in [the declaration] without distinction of any kind such as race, color, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion national or social origin, property, birth or other status.*”²⁰

Later international and regional treaties, including the ICESCR²¹, ICCPR²², and the African Charter²³, have all emphasized this prohibition. The concept of “other status,” which is contained in all these treaties, applies to discrimination on grounds of disability²⁴. At a minimum, this requirement entails that nobody should be discriminated insofar as access to the rights in these treaties²⁵. Any discrimination of a LWD is, therefore, a violation of his or her rights. At the regional level, *the*

¹⁷ See CRPD, supra note 12, art. 24(1).

¹⁸ See id. art. 5(2).

¹⁹ See id. art 5, 24(2)(c).

²⁰ UDHR, supra note 7, art. 2.

²¹ See ICESCR, supra note 9, art. 2(2) (“The States Parties to the present Covenant undertake to guarantee that the rights enunciated in the present Covenant will be exercised without discrimination of any kind as to race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status.”).

²² See ICCPR, supra note 8, art. 26 (“All persons are equal before the law and are entitled without any discrimination to the equal protection of the law. In this respect, the law shall prohibit any discrimination and guarantee to all persons equal and effective protection against discrimination on any ground such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status.”).

²³ See African Charter, supra note 11, art. 2.

²⁴ See General Comment No. 20, ESCOR, 15, E/C.12/GC/20 (July 2, 2009).

²⁵ See General Comment No. 5, CESCR, 5, E/1995/22 (Dec. 9, 1994).

Commission on the African Charter on Peoples and Human Rights (Commission) in Purohit and Moore v. The Gambia²⁶ discussed this entitlement. While underscoring the need to eradicate discrimination in practice, the Commission observed that LWDs, like any other learner, have “hopes, dreams, and goals.”²⁷

These need to be safeguarded at all times²⁸. Some writers have discussed the concept of discrimination against LWDs through offering examples. Ruth Bukola, for instance, defines this term to include denial of admission into and inaccessibility of the physical environment in academic institutions²⁹.

This approach may be narrow in the sense that it may exclude other discriminatory practices that LWDs continue to face. The perspective taken at the international level is a bit different. Rather than illustrations, the focus at this level has been placed on actions that would constitute discrimination and their potential outcomes. Both elements in this two-part test have to be satisfied in order for one to make a finding of discrimination based on disability. ***In its General Comment No. 5 of 1994, the U.N. Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR) defined disability-based discrimination to include “[a]ny distinction, exclusion, restriction or preference or denial of reasonable accommodation based on disability which has the effect of nullifying or impairing the recognition, enjoyment, or exercise of socio-economic, social or cultural rights.”³⁰***

A similar definition exists in Article 2 of the CRPD. ***This treaty reiterates that same two-part test. Discrimination against LWDs under this article means “[a]ny distinction, exclusion or restriction on the basis of disability which has the purpose or effect of impairing or nullifying the recognition, enjoyment or exercise, on an equal basis with others, of all human rights and fundamental freedoms in the political, economic, social, cultural, civil or any other field. It includes all forms of discrimination, including denial of reasonable accommodation.”³¹*** The phrase “reasonable accommodation” is key in the area of disability studies because it is a central tool in the realization of the right to education for LWDs.

Owing to its importance, a significant amount of literature has been generated while exploring the meaning of this norm and its application in general and within specific

²⁶ Purohit and Moore v. The Gambia, Communication 241/2001, Afr. Comm’n Hum. & Peoples’ Rhts. (May 15-29, 2003).

²⁷ Id. 61.

²⁸ 38. Id.

²⁹ Ruth Bukola, The Right to Inclusive Education in Nigeria: Meeting the Needs and Challenges of Children with Disabilities, 10 AFR. HUM. RTS. L.J. 457, 459 (2010) (discussing children with disabilities in Africa and their educational needs).

³⁰ General Comment No. 5, supra note 35, 15.

³¹ CRPD, supra note 12, art. 2.

settings. The next section of this article further discusses this principle. For now, it is important to note that this phrase, as the CRPD defines, means ***“[n]ecessary and appropriate modification and adjustments not imposing a disproportionate or undue burden where needed in a particular case, to ensure to [LWDs] the enjoyment or exercise on an equal basis with others of all human rights and freedoms.”***³² ***In General Comment No. 20, the CESCR expounded further the concept of discrimination in the context of disability, as it focused on the concept of “reasonable accommodation.”*** According to the committee, “denial of reasonable accommodation” is a “prohibited form of discrimination on the basis of disability,”³³ which international and domestic laws prohibit.

An Overview of Disability Statistics in Education and their Meaning to Disability Inclusion

Uganda’s population is estimated to be 45.9 million persons in 2024.³⁴, according to Uganda National Household Survey (UNHS) 2024, and 5.7% of the population of Uganda has a disability. However, ***this figure has been disputed by disability rights groups, who claim that it is lower than the 12.4% recorded in the 2014 census.***³⁵ ***The UNHS statistics show a significant percentage increase of disabled people from the National Population Census Report 2014 which stated that disabled people were 12.4% of the population.***³⁶ The increasing proportion of disabled people appears to be a global development. According to the 2024 Global Economics of Disability Report, there are 1.6 billion people with disabilities in the world. This is more than the long known estimates that 16% of the world population is disabled people.³⁷

However, in Uganda, it appears that the increasing awareness about disability is not reflected in education. If it is reflected, then, what disability discrimination means in education is lacking. To support that observation, 55% of persons with disabilities were literate compared to 75 percent of those without disabilities (UBOS, 2019)³⁸ On literacy levels, evidence from statistics suggests that the illiteracy levels among

³² Id.

³³ General Comment No. 20, supra note 34, 28.

³⁴ Uganda Bureau of Statistics (UBOS), 2024 Statistical Abstract, ‘Midyear Population Projections.

³⁵ UBOS, Uganda National Household Survey 2024.

³⁶ The percentage was computed by the researcher using the data provided.

³⁷ https://www.who.int/health-topics/disability#tab=tab_1

³⁸

https://uganda.unfpa.org/sites/default/files/pub-pdf/disability_inclusion_-_factsheet._final.pdf

disabled people are higher than those who are not disabled. Moreover, there are currently 113 Special Needs Education schools across the country, though not in all districts of Uganda. Most are in fact run by non-governmental organizations and faith-based organizations, calling into question issues of quality and consistency.³⁹

Figure 41: School attendance among children aged 5-17 years by disability

Source: Based on own calculations using Disability Situational Analysis Household Survey 2019

Despite the political will to promote inclusive schools, there is limited budget and resources directed towards ensuring all children with disabilities can attend inclusive mainstream schools. While Uganda is one of the few low-income countries that has a specific budget allocation for children with disabilities, these budget lines do not clearly indicate whether finances are for special or inclusive education. This is important as it relates to the additional costs of disability, in particular the use of additional resources in the classroom, including classroom assistants or support teachers. Moreover, the budget is only 0.1% of the overall education budget. Uganda has a range of school settings, including “fully inclusive” schools, integrated units (whereby children are taught in a separate unit within a mainstream school, but play with the other children at breaks etc) and special schools (usually impairment-specific, such as schools for the Deaf). The permitted ratio of students to teachers in mainstream schools is currently 45:1. However, classrooms often exceed this, making inclusion of children with disabilities even more difficult. Of the few children with a disability that do access education, 5 percent access it within an inclusive setting in regular schools, while 10 per cent access it through special

³⁹<https://www.developmentpathways.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Webready-DP1294-ESP-Disability-Uganda-Sept-2020.pdf>

schools and annexes. This means that the remaining children who are attending school are not receiving any specific interventions or support. Special needs education is underfunded and poorly mainstreamed across the school system, and many special schools are of poor quality and/or high cost.⁴⁰

Secondary

Research indicates that children with disabilities – particularly girls with disabilities – do enroll in school but drop out at increasing numbers across the school years. This is due to a range of factors, including a lack of specialist teachers, a lack of accommodations in the classroom, violence, and pregnancy (Nyende 2012, Moi 2012, Devries et al 2014). For parents, cost is a significant factor in the decision of whether or not to send their children to school. During the qualitative research, some parents with disabilities also emphasized that they did not trust the quality of government schools, and that they preferred to save up enough money to send their children to private school instead. Alex and Otis’ stories, is one example of this.

Alex, who rents land in order to grow maize, prefers to save up and send his 13 year old son to a private school, paying fees of UGX 70,000 per term, as he and his wife think he “would get a better education” there.

Another man, Otis, who is 57 years old, sends his youngest son to a private school, but struggles to pay the fees. When asked why he did not send his son to a government school, he laughed in derision. Almost everyone interviewed noted the costs attached to free universal education.

As the Figure indicates, despite the stated preference of sending their children to private schools, the household survey results show that the majority of students with and without disabilities attend government-run schools in all regions. The exception is in the Central region, where students are more likely to attend private schools. In most regions, young persons with disabilities are more likely to attend government schools than students without disabilities, with the exception of the Northern region.⁴¹

Although the higher education sector was experiencing these challenges, the government was making progress in development of the infrastructure for inclusive education. Notably, an institute- Uganda National Institute for Special Education (UNISE), now a faculty of ***Special Needs and Rehabilitation at Kyambogo University*** was developed to train teachers on special needs education. This has no doubt contributed to widening access to education by disabled pupils especially under the universal primary education (UPE) programme. As more disabled pupils are joining secondary education, inclusive secondary education by mainstreaming of

⁴⁰ Id 39.

⁴¹<https://www.developmentpathways.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Webready-DP1294-ESP-Disability-Uganda-Sept-2020.pdf>

disabled pupils, especially the deaf or the blind is progressively being developed at secondary level O education and as well as at Primary Teacher Colleges.

Despite the annual increasing number of institutions and enrolment, higher education still continues facing numerous challenges: congestion of classrooms; congestion of halls of residence; strikes by both lecturers and students especially in public universities; inadequate supply of teaching materials and inadequate reading materials in the libraries, working space, recreational facilities, and accommodation for students and office space for administrations.⁴² Many higher education institutions, especially the private ones, operate in rented premises which are overcrowded and have very poor facilities.⁴³

Reports of experiences of disabled people in these institutions are lacking, But according to the experience of this researcher, these reforms were not taking account of disabled people because, around that time, awareness about disability was still low and disabled people were few in these institutions. The reform process itself appeared unplanned and forcefully implemented as such influencing it to take account of disability was not easy. It appears therefore, higher education is not prepared to receive disabled students, yet, and more disabled people are joining it. This means innovations such as reasonable accommodation for disabled students⁴⁴ appear not a key issue in the institutions.

Scope of the Disability Legislation and its Provisions on Higher Education

The 1995 Constitution of Uganda as amended-

This is the Grund norm, a supreme national instrument providing for the rights of persons with disabilities in Uganda. The following are the common articles of the Constitution, which promote the respect of rights of persons with disabilities:

Objective vi: The State shall ensure gender balance and fair representation of marginalised groups on all constitutional and other bodies;

Objective xvi: The State and society shall recognise the rights of persons with disabilities to respect and human dignity;

Objective xxiv: The state shall promote the development of sign language for the deaf;

⁴² JC Kwesiga and J Ahikire, 'On Student Access and Equity in Reforming University: Makerere in the 1990s and Beyond' [2006] 4 JHEA /RESA accessed on 10th August 2008.

⁴³ National Council for Higher Education (n40), page 27.

⁴⁴ <https://etheses.whiterose.ac.uk/6863/1/Paul%20Emong%20PhD%20thesis.pdf>

Article 21(1): All persons are equal before and under the law in all spheres of political, economic and social and cultural life and in every other respect and shall enjoy equal protection of the law;

Article 21(2): A person shall not be discriminated against on the basis of sex, race, colour, ethnic origin, tribe, birth, creed or religion or social economic standing, political opinion or disability;

Article 32(1): The state shall take affirmative action in favour of groups marginalized on the basis of gender, age, disability or any other reasons created by history, tradition or custom for the purpose of addressing imbalances which exist against them.

Article 35 (1): Persons with disabilities have a right to respect and human dignity and the state and society shall take appropriate measures to ensure they realize their full mental and physical potential;

Article 35(2) Parliament shall enact laws appropriate for the protection of Persons with Disabilities Article 32, provides for Affirmative Action, the state shall take affirmative action in favour of groups marginalised on the basis of gender, age, disability or any other reason created by history, tradition or custom, for the purpose of redressing imbalances which exist against them.

Article 35 of the 1995 Constitution as amended provides for Rights of persons with disabilities it provides that Persons with disabilities have a right to respect and human dignity and the State and society shall take appropriate measures to ensure that they realise their full mental and physical potential. It goes further to provide **under Clause 2**, Parliament shall enact laws appropriate for the protection of persons with disabilities.

Below is the pie-chart showing different disability percentages in Uganda.

SOURCE: Children with disabilities in Uganda, the hidden reality.

On education, the constitution guarantees that all persons have a right to education.⁷³ The spirit of the constitution as indicated by its principle **objective XVIII places** an obligation on government to promote free and compulsory basic education, take appropriate measures to afford every citizen equal opportunity to attain the highest educational standards possible and allow individuals or groups freedom to found and operate educational institutions within the general educational policy. This mirrors the provisions on education in the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), article 13. It also applies to disabled people by virtue of the generality of constitutional rights. In particular, it provides a background for operationalisation of article 24 of CRPD on education as Uganda is a State party to the CRPD. However, the constitution does not provide specific ways how the realisation of this right is to be enforced.

Non discrimination in the provision of education services-PWDA

2020

(1) An institution of learning shall not discriminate against a learner with a disability, on the basis of the disability.

(2) Subsection (1) does not apply where an institution of learning is established for learners of a specific disability, and the learner does not have that disability. (3) An institution of learning discriminates against a learner with a disability where—

- (a) on the basis of the disability, the institution of learning refuses to accept an application for admission, made by the learner with a disability who is otherwise qualified for admission;
- (b) the conditions for admission to the institution of learning exclude the admission of learners with disabilities;
- (c) the institution of learning denies or limits access of a learner with a disability, to the available facilities and services;
- (d) the institution of learning expels a learner with a disability, on the basis of the disability; or
- (e) the institution of learning subjects the learner with a disability to any unfair treatment, on the basis of the disability.

(4) An institution of learning that enrolls a learner with a disability shall—

- (a) provide an inclusive education system for the learner; and*
- (b) make the necessary structural adjustments to the buildings and premises of the institution of learning, to enable access to the building or premises by a learner with a disability, within three months from the date of admission of the learner.*

(5) In addition to the requirements under subsection (4), an institution of learning which is owned or aided by Government that enrolls a learner with a disability, shall provide sign language services, learning instructional materials and assistive devices, suitable for the learner and required for examinations by the learner.

(6) A parent or guardian of a child with a disability has the responsibility of enrolling the child in an institution of learning or ensuring that the child is enrolled in an institution of learning.

Table of enrollment in Secondary school students with Special Needs (2007-2010)

Year/ Class	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	Tot al	% of enrolm ent
2007	2,9 90	2,5 55	2,5 33	2,1 25	1,0 54	84 6	12, 103	1.3
2008	2,8 30	2,6 89	2,1 28	1,8 31	86 2	80 5	11, 145	1
2009	3,2 75	3,0 52	2,8 97	2,0 83	1,1 72	93 9	13, 418	1.1
2010	3,2 08	3,0 11	2,6 32	2,2 46	1,0 53	84 3	12, 993	1.1

Out of 1,370,583 students enrolled in a secondary school in Uganda, 8,945 students (0.6%) have special learning needs. Visually impaired students comprise the largest share of these students, followed by those with physical disabilities. Pupils with autism and multiple handicaps were fewer among enrolled students. There is no data available on students with disabilities enrolled in universities and other tertiary⁴⁵ institutions. There is an urgent need for such data to ensure equitable access to tertiary education.⁴⁶ The form of treatment given to people with disability has not been encouraging of late. A July report released by the National Council on Disability (NCD) indicated 55 percent of persons with disabilities lacked functional literacy skills, and only 33 percent studied to primary grade seven⁴⁷.

Affirmative Action

⁴⁵ (UNICEF, 2014).

⁴⁶ Special Needs Education in Uganda: Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) #4 Concerns Quality and Inclusive Education, February 7, 2020

⁴⁷ Uganda 2012 Human Rights Report (Report). Bureau of Democracy, Human Rights, and Labor. 2012

The focus of this research is on the provisions concerning disability and higher education, provided for in the UTIA2001 (Amendments 2003 and 2006) and the Equal Opportunities Commission Act (EOCA) 2007.

The UTIA establishes the National Council for Higher Education (NCHE)⁴⁸ to regulate higher education and advise the government on higher education in accordance with existing education policy and legal framework.⁴⁹ On disability inclusion, the UTIA provides for the promotion of equality of opportunities for disabled people in higher education as below.

It provides for the representation of a disabled person on the NCHE Board.⁵⁰ Definitely, such representation is aimed at creating awareness about disability inclusion to NCHE, so that, in its regulatory role, NCHE ensures institutions of higher education mainstream disability. While this is the indisputable intent, it is submitted that awareness alone cannot be a guarantee that NCHE takes into account the needs of disabled people in its policies, as awareness does not necessarily translate into action and imposes no obligation. Given that every level of education records a high dropout rate for disabled people, this means the inclusion of disabled people in education requires more specific action than other groups. In that respect, it is suggested that the UTIA should have enhanced NCHE further on matters of disability inclusion by buttressing representation with specific obligations on NCHE to bring about disability equality. This would make the Statutory Instruments issued by NCHE explicit on disability inclusion and thus render them enforceable and capable of being monitored in a bid to assess compliance. Particular requirements would be that the institutions' facilities are accessible to disabled people and that teaching takes account of the needs of disabled people.

In the light of the functions and the regulatory powers of NCHE over the institutions, specifically on disability inclusion, it would emphasise accessibility and ensure institutions comply with the minimum requirements in the PwDA 2020, so enforcing the Act.

Access to Physical Facilities *Physical facilities* play a key role in the learning process of any institution. These facilities are the channels through which the learning process occurs. Several activities take place within these spaces, namely, learners receive instructions, they interact with their colleagues and faculty as well as non-teaching personnel, examinations are conducted, and learners are able to travel around the institution as well as gain access to research materials. Accessing

⁴⁸ Object of the Act of UTIA 2001.

⁴⁹ UTIA s 5.

⁵⁰ Ibid 2001 s 7(j).

these facilities, hence, becomes crucial for any learner. In order to meet the legal requirements, the university must ensure all facilities are not only within reach, but that all learners can access them with relative ease.

Library Access-

Access to education requires availability of facilities, including libraries. The preamble to the CRPD provides that accessibility of the physical environment, including libraries, is important in enabling LWDs realize their right to education. Generally speaking, these spaces provide learners with a quiet place to study or conduct research. Access to the library is, thus, very important to any student. For these spaces to be of use to LWDs they must be accessible. Access for this category of learners means they can gain entry into a library and retrieve any records that are held.

As an implementation framework, these regulations would also define how the respective obligations in the statute were to be implemented, with clear modalities. At present, an overview of the existing regulations⁵¹ indicates that they are not explicit on disability inclusion, except for one on the library buildings.⁵² This calls for the clarification of the role of NCHE in relation to disability inclusion.

On institutions of higher education, UTIA requires them to give the opportunity of acquiring higher education to all people wishing to do so, including persons with disabilities.⁵³ It also requires institutions to provide accessible physical facilities to the users of the public university.⁵⁴ On admission to higher education, ***UTIA states the Admission Committee of a Public University shall take into consideration affirmative action in favour of marginalised groups on the basis of gender, disability and disadvantaged schools.***⁵⁵ It also offers similar consideration to persons with special talents in sports, music and other social activities for their enhancement.⁵⁶

⁵¹ Since 2005, the NCHE has issued 10 regulations on effective management of tertiary institutions of education. accessed on 17th October 2010.

⁵² The Universities and Other Tertiary Institutions (Institutional Standards) Regulations, 2005, par. 11(1)

⁵³ UTIA s 24(1) (b).

⁵⁴ Ibid s 24(1) (c).

⁵⁵ Ibid s 28(3).

⁵⁶ Ibid s28(4).

*15+ years; **21+ years; Ω24+ years (ages groups restricted to 3+ years above the expected age for completion, i.e. 12 years for primary and 18 years for secondary); Data source: 2016 Uganda DHS data analyzed for this report.⁵⁷

School attendance among people of secondary school age (13-18 years) Figure 3 and Table A2 in the appendix present current school attendance among people of secondary school age (13-18 years) from the 2016 Uganda DHS data analyzed for this report. **Youth with disabilities were more likely to be out of school (44%) compared to their peers without disabilities (27%). Overall, secondary school attendance (i.e. proportion attending secondary school out of those of secondary school age) was lower (9%) among youth with disabilities compared to youth without disabilities (19%).**

⁵⁷ <https://mastercardfdn.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Uganda-Report.pdf>

Figure 3. School attendance among 13-18 years

Table 1. Notable provisions related to the education of youth with disabilities in policy and law

Notable Provisions	Policy & Law
People with disabilities have a right to education free from discrimination	Constitution; Persons with Disabilities Act 2019
Learners with disabilities have a right to be taught together with other learners in the same environment, and if required, be given extra support appropriate for their disability	Persons with Disabilities Act 2019
Institutes with learners with disabilities must make the necessary structural adjustments to the building and facilities to make it accessible	Persons with Disabilities Act 2019
Public institutes that enrol learners with disabilities must provide support such as sign language services, assistive devices, and accessible learning materials	Persons with Disabilities Act 2019
Government shall provide special facilities, tools, and equipment throughout the country for the training of people with disabilities	Equal Opportunity Commission Act 2007
Public institutes that enrol learners with disabilities must provide support such as sign language services, assistive devices, and accessible learning materials	Persons with Disabilities Act 2019
Any discriminatory practices shall be monitored by the Equal Opportunity Commission	Equal Opportunity Commission Act 2007

The disability policy framework in Uganda is strengthening and provides the basis for advocacy promoting and protecting the rights of persons with disabilities. In 2020, the Persons with Disabilities Act came into effect, providing a framework for inclusive policy and services.

Policies related to education are typically spearheaded by the Ministry of Education and Sports, with contributions from other government agencies and OPDs. Noted by KIs as important to education is the Marrakesh Treaty, an international treaty that promotes access of copyright material for people with a visual impairment. This was noted as having the potential to vastly improve access for students with disabilities through textbooks and other materials in accessible formats such as braille, tactile, large-print, and audio editions. However, although the Government of Uganda ratified the Treaty in 2018, it has not been domesticated.

There is also an upcoming National Inclusive Education Policy, currently under draft. When approved, KIs believed this could offer strong guidelines, allocation of financial resources, and monitoring of disability inclusion in education. KIs noted how this will prompt education institutions to provide a learner-friendly environment that is responsive to the different needs of learners with disabilities, and in turn, improve their attendance and effective participation. This policy was developed in consultation (through meetings) with stakeholders that included educators, parents, children with disabilities, and OPDs (such as the Uganda National Association for the Blind, Uganda National Action on Physical Disability, National Union of Disabled Persons in Uganda, Uganda Society for Disabled Children).

KIs also noted the provision for affirmative action under the Universities and Tertiary Institutions Act (2001) where persons with disabilities receive an additional four points to what they have acquired through Advanced Level exams. This allows them to better reach entry requirements for public universities or tertiary institutions, as well as being eligible for government financing schemes. One KI noted that every year, 64 scholarships are available for persons with disabilities overall in tertiary institutions. Though many have benefited from this, there is still limited awareness of this provision, and many cannot afford to come to Kampala to obtain the required recommendation from the National Union of Persons with Disabilities in Uganda (NUDIPU) to apply for these scholarships.

In February 2022, the Ministry of Education and Sports announced an increase in scholarships for students with disabilities during the launch of Uganda's commitments to the Global Disability Summit. The number of scholarships is set to increase from 64 to 320 in more than 20 public universities. The Ministry also cited plans to advocate for scholarships to private universities [18]. Currently, affirmative action applies only to students joining universities to pursue degree courses. Those in Technical and Vocational Education and Training are not currently considered.

Challenges encountered in the the provision of support services to students with disabilities

According to Funk and Wagnall (2016), obstacles can make it difficult or impossible for an individual or a group of people, whether they have impairments or not, to achieve their goals. Various legislation developed at the national and international levels have contributed to an increase in the number of students with disabilities admitted to following the courses of their choosing around the world to date. The provision of necessary services and meeting the educational needs of kids with

disabilities remains unchanged, despite tremendous efforts. These include converting textbooks to electronic formats for certain groups of students, providing sign language interpreters and captioning at campus events for those who are deaf or blind, and providing support to some students who require voice recognition technology such as voice input software, which allows them to speak into a microphone and the commands and texts are related to the computer, especially those who are unable to use a standard keyboard due to motor or visual impairments (Anittos and McLusk, 2008).

The expensive expense of technology makes it impossible for the university to finance it, forcing visually impaired and cerebral palsy students to seek aid from their guides or classmates in finding material and assisting in the transcription of Braille work to print format (Kwame, 2011). Emong (2014) asserts that the overall environment of higher education is unaffected by the accessibility requirements of admitted students with disabilities. He asserts that assessment procedures and library services are not easily accessible to students with disabilities at higher education institutions. The reason for limiting access to material that can be utilized to complete coursework, quizzes, and exams (Conway, 2010)

Challenges encountered in the provision of education support services to students with disabilities

An overview of the Faculties' Reasonable Accommodation Measures(Prof. Paul Emong PHD Research Analysis)

Regarding the challenges encountered in providing education support services to students with disabilities. Data collected showed that the following issues hampered students with disabilities: a lack of permanent support staff, difficulties in communicating, accessibility issues, unfavorable attitudes, and poor cleanliness. When support staff became available, they were hired under ambiguous conditions⁵⁸. Additionally, as one participant pointed out, they were not in proportion to the number of students in need of their services in the various faculties who had impairments and other special needs;

One of the challenges we have is the recruitment of sighted guides and sign language interpreters. They are not talked about anywhere in the staff structure. So students who are deaf or visually impaired admitted are compelled to come along with their own people who could either be their brothers, sisters or

⁵⁸<https://kyuspace.kyu.ac.ug/xmlui/bitstream/handle/20.500.12504/1213/ACHIENG%20CHRISTINE%202022.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

course mates to work as guides or interpreters because of their scarcity, one interpreter is forced to interpret for students with hearing impairment in so many lectures single handedly as a result, the interpreter gets worn out and decides to disappear leaving students to go for a period of a week or so without interpretation services. Sometimes I do not know what we can do for these students. (L5)

The study outcomes indicated that students experienced communication challenges as expressed by one of the participants that;

At times I have to write down what I want because I cannot communicate using sign language with students and lecturers which hinder me from airing out my views in response to certain things that affect me as an individual. (SH3)

Discussion with the staff revealed that a number of approaches have been applied by the staff to support disabled students access to learning. The common approach is giving extra time to disabled students in coursework and examinations. Others reported that they encouraged other students to assist disabled students in any way possible in accessing lectures. Other approaches depend on the requirements of each disability.

For students with mobility problems, their overall impediment in accessing lecture rooms is the physical inaccessibility of buildings as noted earlier on, on access to accommodation. Other than the recently constructed buildings, all the old buildings which contain a bulk of university lecture rooms are to some extent inaccessible to people with mobility difficulties, more so most are storied. How the needs of disabled students are accommodated in this scenario depends on the considerations of those who draw the teaching timetable and allocate lecture rooms.

For the visually impaired students, the academic staff noted that there was a lack of facilities for them to support the visually impaired students in learning and in assessment. During examinations, if warranting, a blind student does it in a separate room and the questions read to him/her by the invigilator.

For the deaf, those who are hard of hearing are requested to sit in front during the lecture.

The research found that there is willingness among staff or existence of internal initiatives to support disabled students. It was evident from the discussions that the faculties' measures are mainly reactive _reasonable accommodation' measure.

Nothing special is offered to disabled students, except we are considerate when setting the level of achievement for practical activities. Disabled students though not officially given concessions during practical classes and during assessment of practical are considered differently depending on their disability.⁵⁹

The lack of an established mechanism for inclusion of disabled people is attributable to the fact no university has a disability policy and also the lack of a directive on disability issues from the central university authorities.

Consequently, the requirement that institutions teaching methods should change towards enhancing equality of opportunity for disabled students appears not part of the institutional teaching and learning policies, and most likely not also in discussions at department and course level. According to disabled students interviewed, the mode of delivering lectures and assessment is limiting their access to academic programmes.

Implementation gaps and challenges

While policies and legislation, such as the 2020 Disability Act, may be used to hold duty-bearers accountable for implementing disability inclusive programmes, no KIs were able to cite examples of successes. There is the potential for policies to improve lives of people with disabilities, but only through advocacy efforts to prompt its implementation.

KIs described the government's slow pace in operationalising policies and passing implementation guidelines. Overall, the interviews indicate that as much as the existence of policies highlights an equity-driven government agenda, the extent to which they are being put in practice is unclear. This is partly due to lack of disability-disaggregated data, which makes it hard for the government to appropriately plan and budget for persons with disabilities. Key informants, therefore, suggested that the government needed to create and use databases that allow disaggregation of relevant indicators by disability status.

Additionally, interviews with KIs highlighted several other factors that impact education policy implementation:

i) Exclusion from school at a young age

⁵⁹ Academic staff of public university 2.

KIs told us that children with disabilities are less likely to be taken to school or are often only able to join late into the school system. Several factors contribute to this, such as negative beliefs about disability, inability to cover school fees, and lack of access to assistive devices. Once they miss enrolling in school at a younger age, it becomes difficult for them to complete education and eventually gain employment. As the KI *below notes, even delayed progression has an impact on learners with disabilities.*

“You should also know that at times persons with disabilities take long to join school. Someone can join primary one when he is eight or seven years old because of different factors. One would be that the parents didn’t have the motive to send him/ her to school. Two, they may not have what they need to go to school. [...] By the time people decide to let the child join primary school, they will be around six years old, sitting with children of two or three years.” (Representative from an OPD)

ii) Assessments focused on academic performance

According to KIs, the school system tends to focus solely on academic performance, limiting progressions for some learners with disabilities who may struggle in these areas, but potentially thrive in others. This is likely contributing to dropouts among youth with disabilities.

“There are some children who come to school and study up to a certain class for example, now they are saying it's automatic promotion in government schools [Primary] 1 to [Primary] 7. When you want to join [Senior] 1, the condition is that when you want to continue to [Senior] 1 and the government has to pay for you, you have to get 28 marks. Now how about that person who will never get 28 even if he spent five more years in primary? He is excluded at that level.” (Representative from government)

iii) Inaccessible learning environments

Although there are policies in place requiring all government education institutions to be physically accessible, standards are often not followed. For example, ramps, hallways, door frames, toilets, rails, and clear signage are often inaccessible or unavailable. Further, few accessible learning materials are available in schools, including large print books for students with a visual impairment. Sign language interpreters are also rare. The Ministry of Education and Sports have announced their intention to provide more equipment and assistive technology to students with disabilities, based on assessments of need.

iv) Lack of support for teachers

Several policies are focused on maintaining teacher standards, particularly in addressing learners with special needs. These include the National Teacher Policy, the Universal Primary Education policy, and the Universal Secondary Education policy. However, there is a need to support teachers to better identify and respond to learners with disabilities. There is a lack of training, materials, and guidelines to support teachers in making learning inclusive.

“We also still have a challenge of preparing teachers in educational institutions to accept and to welcome all learners in schools. We need them to be able to identify learners with special needs. We went to school of over 1000 learners and asked if they have students or pupils with disabilities and they tell you that they don’t have such students, when actually they are there but are not identified. So, there is that gap, we need to give these people some tips, some skills of identifying learners with special needs and disabilities so that they are able to work with them.” (Representative from government)

As part of Uganda’s commitments to the Global Disability Summit, the Ministry of Education and Sports announced intent to conduct teacher capacity building sessions on inclusive education practices, but these efforts are currently in development and have not yet been implemented.

v) Inadequate promotion of inclusive education models

According to KIs, there is a need to promote inclusive education as opposed to special needs education where learners with disabilities are restricted to specialised institutions. This, they argue, has several far-reaching consequences ranging from limiting disability awareness amongst nondisabled people, to restricting the confidence of learners with disabilities in operating amongst people without disabilities.⁶⁰

“There should be inclusive education, I don’t believe in special needs education. People will not understand our needs if we are confined in one place. Some of us who have gone through mainstream education, we are better off than those who went through special needs schools. This is because their confidence is very low, they can’t speak in public, they are always emotional. But when you are confronted with challenges like discrimination and then you show your peers in school that that’s not who I am, I am a human being like you. When you perform very well in class, they start coming closer to you and they will realize that actually they aren’t as clever as you are. So they start appreciating disability in diversity.” (Representative from an OPD)

⁶⁰ <https://mastercardfdn.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Uganda-Report.pdf>

Conclusion

Uganda has a progressive disability legislative framework and is in three strands - the constitutional guarantees on disability equality, provisions on disability in other equality laws and disability-specific Acts of Parliament. In terms of bringing equal access for disabled people in higher education, the legal framework provides substantive mechanisms on how that can be achieved. However, the implementation of the law is largely on a promotional basis by DRGs rather than enforcement by government. Another weakness is that much of the efforts to realize disability rights in the country is being done through affirmative action principles. The challenge with that approach is that affirmative action lacks definitive ways of eliminating systemic disability discrimination.

The PwDA 2020 through its provisions on discrimination of disabled people in educational services, making the educational environment accessible and promotion of educational development of disabled brings Uganda disability legal framework broadly into line with the CRPD on education. However, the challenge is that the language used in the Act makes it challenging to enforce. Also, its meaning of discrimination in education particularly in relation to the duty to provide reasonable accommodation is lacking. It is also evident from the chapter that more disabled people will soon be joining higher education. However, the situation in higher education is worrying as the legislation appears to be not fully interpreted to bring about equality, access and inclusion of disabled people. The law therefore should be enhancing such initiatives by requiring institutions to undertake a duty to provide reasonable accommodation to disabled people and this is the requirement of the CRPD.

Based on the study findings, it was discovered that the university predominantly supported admitted students with disabilities who were sponsored by the government. The availed support, ranged from psycho-social, financial to material support to facilitate their academic endeavors and their general welfare while at campus and dispensed funds to students under the Private Scheme to enable them purchase mobility assistive devices. This discriminatory support emanated from what the University disability policy stated regarding support services to privately sponsored students.

Raising from the existing University policies and the level of awareness that the officials of the institution have in relation to matters pertaining to disability inclusions. However, due to a lack of resources and established processes to guarantee that concerns involving students with disabilities are taken into account by the University on its priority list, this awareness has not increased as anticipated. The University's standards, which were ambiguous on the mainstreaming of handicap issues, can be held responsible for the lack of established methods. Into the bargain, the University lacked permanent support personnel. Those who were available were hired on unclear terms and were not proportionate to the number of students with disabilities which hindered their participation in the University programmes and activities. The University Council urgently needed to embrace excellent opportunities and reasonable accommodations as processes to improve accommodating practices designed to achieve disability inclusion as specified by the provisions in the National and International Legislations.

Recommendations

The following recommendations must be made in light of the study's findings:

A. Recommendations for the University

1. The University should recruit proficient sighted guides, Braille transcribers, helpers and sign language interpreters proportionate to the number of admitted students.
2. The University should plan, budget and procure sports equipment that suit National and International Standards for Students with Disabilities in Institutions of Higher Education.
3. New provisions that are conscious of the social and economic needs of Students with Disabilities be made to public University Policies to enhance disability inclusion.
4. The University should intensify awareness raising workshops for the teaching and non-teaching staff across all Faculties on disability related matters and empower them with basic skills in sign language, Braille and ICT for persons with disabilities.
5. The University should ensure that adjustments are made to the physical infrastructure so that they are accessible to all students.
6. The University should set aside funds to procure adequate ICT, disability resource rooms and have equipment in the library adapted to suit students with disabilities.

B. Recommendations for lecturers

7. Lecturers should orient themselves to employ accommodative practices during lectures that cater for all Students with Disabilities.
8. Sports coaches and trainers should motivate themselves and acquire capacity building in modern sports techniques to enable public Universities sports teams to meet the National and International disability sports set standards.
9. Lecturers should encourage Students with Disabilities to sit in appropriate locations in lecture rooms during lectures.
10. To avert limited access to information, lecturers should develop teaching and learning materials and have it adapted in accessible formats that cater for students' diverse study needs.

C. Recommendations for Students with Disabilities.

11. Students with Disabilities should encourage each other to open up and relate among themselves and the entire University student body.
12. Students with Disabilities are advised to take part in sports and recreational activities, using the availed support personnel.
13. Students with Disabilities should actively be involved in disability empowerment workshops, advocacy, University political leadership and governance other than those stipulated in the affirmative scheme of the University.
14. Students with disabilities are urged to inform university administrators of their difficulties so that they can be resolved by using the leadership of the disabled students' association and their representatives to the guild council.

Suggestion for further research

This study scope was limited in a number of ways, including its geographic breadth and content coverage. Therefore, it is advised that future study in this field be conducted with a greater geographic coverage and broaden its content breadth.

REFERENCES

Abimanyi-Ochom, J., & Mannan, H. (2014). Uganda's disability journey: progress and challenges: community paper. African Journal of

Disability, 3(1), 1-6.

Abraham, S., Stoker, R. G. (2013). 'An evaluation of methods used to teach speech to the hearing impaired using a simulation technique: The transition to inclusion. Journal of the Canadian Association for Leisure. 28 (1), 137-154.

Adoyo, P. O & Odeny, M., L. (2015). Emergent Inclusive education practice in Kenya: challenges and suggestions. International Journal. 2 (6) 47-52

Ainscow, M, Booth, T, & Dyson, A. (2006). Improving Schools, Developing Inclusion. London, England: Routledge.

Ainscow, M. (2015). Struggles for equity in education. The selected works of Mel Ainscow. Routledge.

Amin, M. E. (2005). Social science research methods: Conception, methodology and analysis. Kampala: Makerere University Printery.

Anittos, M. & McLuskie, L. (2008). On Track Toward Inclusive Education. Central Queensland, Australia Commonwealth Consortium for Education. Opportunities for Partnerships in Education in the Commonwealth. Paper for the 15th Commonwealth Conference of Education Ministers: Edinburg, 27-30

Exploring education support services and systems to promote disability inclusion in one selected public university in Uganda by Achieng Christine September, 2022